

The Taxonomic Report

OF THE INTERNATIONAL LEPIDOPTERA SURVEY

ISSN 2643-4776 (print) / ISSN 2643-4806 (online)

A taxonomic list of the Old World genera in the subfamily Hesperinae (Hesperiidae) arranged into tribes

Jing Zhang^{1,2,3}, Qian Cong^{1,3}, Jinhui Shen^{1,2}, Leina Song^{1,2}, and Nick V. Grishin^{1,2*}

Departments of ¹Biophysics, ²Biochemistry, and ³Eugene McDermott Center For Human Growth & Development, University of Texas Southwestern Medical Center, 5323 Harry Hines Blvd., Dallas, TX 75390, USA;

*Corresponding author: grishin@chop.swmed.edu

ABSTRACT. A taxonomic list of valid genera in the subfamily Hesperinae from the Old World assigned to tribes is provided. This list is based on phylogenetic analysis of genomic sequence data complemented by morphological considerations. As a result, there are no *incertae sedis* non-fossil genera in the family Hesperiidae.

Keywords: taxonomy, classification, genomics, phylogeny, biodiversity.

ZooBank registration: <http://zoobank.org/CCF59E03-048E-440A-B310-4830DD2BB5C5>

Here, we summarize tribal assignment for the Old World Hesperinae Latreille, 1809 genera currently regarded as valid (Lees et al. 2003; Warren et al. 2008; Warren et al. 2009; Fan et al. 2016; Toussaint et al. 2018; Cong et al. 2019; Huang et al. 2019; Jiang et al. 2019; Li et al. 2019b; Zhang et al. 2022), with comments about several others. No changes to nomenclature or synonymy are proposed. These results are not new but are mostly scattered throughout our previous publications (Cong et al. 2019; Li et al. 2019a; Zhang et al. 2019; Zhang et al. 2022) and are catalogued here for convenience. The following treatment is deduced from the genomic tree shown in Fig. 1 based on our previously published datasets (Zhang et al. 2022), complemented with morphological considerations. The methods used are detailed in Li (2019a) for experimental work and data processing and in Zhang et al. (2022) for phylogenetic tree construction. Twelve tribes are ordered phylogenetically. Genera are listed alphabetically within each tribe to facilitate visual search. We conclude that presently there are no *incertae sedis* non-fossil genera in the entire family Hesperiidae because all genera have been assigned to tribes. All tribes are monophyletic in our analyses.

Family **Hesperiidae** Latreille, 1809

Subfamily **Hesperinae** Latreille, 1809

Tribe **Aeromachini** Tutt, 1906

Aeromachus Nicéville, 1890

Ampittia Moore, 1881

Arnetta Watson, 1893

Baracus Moore, 1881

Creteus Nicéville, 1895

Halpe Moore, 1878

Halpemorpha Huang, Fan & Chiba, 2019

Lepella Evans, 1937

Onryza Watson, 1893
Pedesta Hemming, 1934
Pithauria Moore, 1878
Praethoressa Huang, Chiba & Fan, 2019
Prosopalpus Holland, 1896
Sebastonyma Watson, 1893
(includes *Parasovia* Devyatkin, 1996)
Sovia Evans, 1949
Thoressa Swinhoe, 1913

Tribe **Ceratrichiini** Grishin, 2019

Argemma Grishin, 2019
Ceratrichia Butler, 1870
Herila Larsen & Collins, 2012
Meza Hemming, 1939
Pardaleodes Butler, 1870
(includes *Ankola* Evans, 1937)

Tribe **Astictopterini** Swinhoe, 1912

Acada Evans, 1937
Acleros Mabilie, 1885
Actinor Watson, 1893
Andronymus Holland, 1896
Artitropa Holland, 1896
Astictopterus C. Felder & R. Felder, 1860
Caenides Holland, 1896
Ceratricula Larsen, 2013
Chondrolepis Mabilie, 1904
Cupitha Moore, 1884
Dotta Grishin, 2019
Eogenes Mabilie, 1909
Flandria Larsen, 2013
Fresna Evans, 1937
Fulda Evans, 1937
Galerga Mabilie, 1898
Gamia Holland, 1896
Gorgyra Holland, 1896
Gyrogra Lindsey & Miller, 1965
Hidari Distant, 1886
Hollandus Larsen & Collins, 2015
Hypoleucis Mabilie, 1891
Isoteinon C. Felder & R. Felder, 1862
Kedestes Watson, 1893
Lennia Grishin, 2022
Leona Evans, 1937
Lissia Grishin, 2019
Melphina Evans, 1937
Melphinyet Larsen, 2012
Moltena Evans, 1937
Monza Evans, 1937
Mopala Evans, 1937
Nervia Grishin, 2019

Noctulana Larsen, 2012
Osmodes Holland, 1892
Osphantes Holland, 1896
Paracleros Berger, 1978
Paronymus Aurivillius, 1925
Parosmodes Holland, 1896
Perrotia Oberthür, 1916
(includes *Miraja* Evans, 1937)
Platylesches Holland, 1896
Pteroteinon Watson, 1893
Rhabdomantis Holland, 1896
Semalea Holland, 1896
Teniorhinus Holland, 1892
Trida Grishin, 2022
Tsitana Evans, 1937
Xanthodisca Aurivillius, 1925
Xanthoneura Eliot, 1978
Xanthonymus Grishin, 2019
Zographetus Watson, 1893
Zophopetes Mabilie, 1904

Tribe **Gretnini** Grishin, 2019

Gretna Evans, 1937

Tribe **Taractrocerini** Voss, 1952

Arrhenes Mabilie, 1904
Banta Evans, 1949
Bibla Mabilie, 1904
Cephrenes Waterhouse & Lyell, 1914
Kobrona Evans, 1935
Mimene Joicey & Talbot, 1917
Ocybadistes Heron, 1894
Oriens Evans, 1932
Pastria Evans, 1949
Potanthus Scudder, 1872
Sabera Swinhoe, 1908
Suniana Evans, 1934
Taractrocera Butler, 1870
Telicota Moore, 1881
Tiacellia Evans, 1949

Tribe **Erionotini** Distant, 1886

Acerbas Nicéville, 1895
Avestia Grishin, 2019
Cerba Grishin, 2019
Erionota Mabilie, 1878
Gangara Moore, 1881
Ge Nicéville, 1895
Hyarotis Moore, 1881
Ilma Swinhoe, 1905
Lotongus Distant, 1886
Matapa Moore, 1881

Oerane Elwes & Edwards, 1897
Pirdana Distant, 1886
Plastingia Butler, 1870
Ploetzia Saalmüller, 1884
Praescobura Devyatkin, 2002
Pseudokerana Eliot, 1978
Pseudopirdana Chiba & Tsukiyama, 1993
Pudicitia Nicéville, 1895
Pyroneura Eliot, 1978
Quedara Swinhoe, 1919
Salanoemia Eliot, 1978
Scobura Elwes & Edwards, 1897
Suada Nicéville, 1895
Suastus Moore, 1881
Unkana Distant, 1886
Zela Nicéville, 1895

Tribe **Notocryptini** Swinhoe, 1913

Ancistroides Butler, 1874
(includes *Notocrypta* Nicéville, 1889 and *Udaspes* Moore, 1881)
Kerana Distant, 1886
Tamela Swinhoe, 1913

Tribe **Ismiini** Grishin, 2022

Iambrix Watson, 1893
Idmon Nicéville, 1895
Isma Distant, 1886

Tribe **Eetionini** Grishin, 2022

Eetion Nicéville, 1895

Tribe **Psolosini** Grishin, 2022

Koruthaialos Watson, 1893
(includes *Stimula* Nicéville, 1898)
Psolos Staudinger, 1889

Tribe **Baorini** Doherty, 1886

Afrogegenes de Jong & Coutsis, 2017
Baoris Moore, 1881
Borbo Evans, 1949
Brusa Evans, 1937
Caltoris Swinhoe, 1893
Gegenes Hübner, [1819]
Iton Nicéville, 1895
Parnara Moore, 1881
Pelopidas Walker, 1870
Polytremis Mabilie, 1904
Prusiana Evans, 1937
Pseudoborbo Lee, 1966
Torbenlarsenia Kemal & Koçak, 2020
(*Larsenia* Chiba, Fan & Sáfián, 2016 is preoccupied)
Tsukiyamaia Zhu, Chiba & Wu, 2016
Zenonia Evans, 1935

Tribe **Hesperiini** Latreille, 1809

Hesperia Fabricius, 1793

Ochlodes Scudder, 1872

Thymelicus Hübner, [1819]

Fig. 1. A phylogenetic tree of representative Hesperinae (mostly type species of their genera) constructed from all protein-coding autosomal genes in the nuclear genome. Specimen/sample codes and general localities are given. The numbers of dataset partitions (Zhang et al. 2022) supporting the branches are shown by corresponding nodes. The tree is folded over to fit on a page, and black arrows guide the direction of viewing. Detailed analysis of the results will be presented elsewhere.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We acknowledge Ping Chen and Ming Tang for excellent technical assistance. We are grateful to David Grimaldi and Courtney Richenbacher (AMNH: American Museum of Natural History, New York, NY, USA), Blanca Huertas, David Lees, and Geoff Martin (BMNH: Natural History Museum, London, UK), Jim Fetzner, Bob Androw, Vanessa Verdecia, Cat Giles, and the late John Rawlins (CMNH: Carnegie Museum of Natural History, Pittsburgh, PA, USA), Weiping Xie (LACM: Los Angeles County Museum of Natural History, Los Angeles, CA, USA), Théo Léger, Wolfram Mey, and Viola Richter (MFNB: Museum für Naturkunde, Berlin, Germany), Rodolphe Rougerie (MNHP: Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France), Matthias Nuss (MTD: Museum für Tierkunde, Dresden, Germany), Jeff Smith and Lynn Kimsey (UCDC: Bohart Museum of Entomology, University of California, Davis, CA, USA), Robert K. Robbins, John M. Burns, and Brian Harris (USNM: National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution, Washington, DC, USA), Axel Hausmann, Andreas Segerer, and Ulf Buchsbaum (ZSMC: Zoologische Staatssammlung München, Germany), for granting access to the collections under their care and stimulating discussions; Ernst Brockmann and Kojiro Shiraiwa for specimens and leg samples, the late Paul A. Opler and Evi Buckner-Opler for collecting specimens under the California Department of Fish and Game permit SC13645; Gerardo Lamas for critical review of the manuscript and correcting several mistakes. We acknowledge the Texas Advanced Computing Center (TACC) at The University of Texas at Austin for providing HPC resources. This study was supported in part by the HHMI Investigator funds and by grants from the National Institutes of Health GM127390 and the Welch Foundation I-1505.

LITERATURE CITED

- Cong, Q., J. Zhang, J. Shen, and N. V. Grishin. 2019. Fifty new genera of HesperIIDae (Lepidoptera). *Insecta Mundi* 0731: 1–56.
- Fan, X., H. Chiba, Z. Huang, W. Fei, M. Wang, and S. Safian. 2016. Clarification of the phylogenetic framework of the tribe Baorini (Lepidoptera: HesperIIDae: HesperIIDae) inferred from multiple gene sequences. *PLoS One* 11(7): e0156861.
- Huang, Z.-F., H. Chiba, J. Jin, A. G. Kizhakke, M. Wang, K. Kunte, and X.-L. Fan. 2019. A multilocus phylogenetic framework of the tribe Aeromachini (Lepidoptera: HesperIIDae: HesperIIDae), with implications for taxonomy and biogeography. *Systematic Entomology* 44(1): 163–178.
- Jiang, W., H. He, Y. Li, Y. Wang, C. Ge, J. Zhu, and W. Yu. 2019. Molecular phylogeny of the butterfly tribe Baorini Doherty, 1886 (HesperIIDae, HesperIIDae) in China. *Zootaxa* 4565(1): 108–116.
- Lees, D. C., C. Kremen, and H. Raharitsimba. 2003. Classification, diversity and endemism of the butterflies (Papilionoidea and Hesperioidea): a revised species checklist. *In*: M., G. S., and J. P. Benstead (Eds.). *The Natural History of Madagascar*. University of Chicago Press; Chicago, pp. 762–793.
- Li, W., Q. Cong, J. Shen, J. Zhang, W. Hallwachs, D. H. Janzen, and N. V. Grishin. 2019a. Genomes of skipper butterflies reveal extensive convergence of wing patterns. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 116(13): 6232–6237.
- Li, Y., J. Zhu, C. Ge, Y. Wang, Z. Zhao, S. Ma, A. A. Hoffmann, N. M. Endersby, Q. Liu, W. Yu, and W. Jiang. 2019b. Molecular phylogeny and historical biogeography of the butterfly tribe Aeromachini Tutt (Lepidoptera: HesperIIDae) from China. *Cells* 8(4): 294.
- Toussaint, E. F. A., J. W. Breinholt, C. Earl, A. D. Warren, A. V. Z. Brower, M. Yago, K. M. Dexter, M. Espeland, N. E. Pierce, D. J. Lohman, and A. Y. Kawahara. 2018. Anchored phylogenomics illuminates the skipper butterfly tree of life. *BMC Evolutionary Biology* 18(1): 101.
- Warren, A. D., J. R. Ogawa, and A. V. Z. Brower. 2008. Phylogenetic relationships of subfamilies and circumscription of tribes in the family HesperIIDae (Lepidoptera: Hesperioidea). *Cladistics* 24(5): 642–676.
- Warren, A. D., J. R. Ogawa, and A. V. Z. Brower. 2009. Revised classification of the family HesperIIDae (Lepidoptera: Hesperioidea) based on combined molecular and morphological data. *Systematic Entomology* 34(3): 467–523.
- Zhang, J., Q. Cong, J. Shen, E. Brockmann, and N. V. Grishin. 2019. Three new subfamilies of skipper butterflies (Lepidoptera, HesperIIDae). *Zookeys* 861: 91–105.
- Zhang, J., Q. Cong, J. Shen, and N. V. Grishin. 2022. Taxonomic changes suggested by the genomic analysis of HesperIIDae (Lepidoptera). *Insecta Mundi* 0921: 1–135.

The Taxonomic Report

is a platinum open access peer-reviewed publication of

The International Lepidoptera Survey (TILS)

The International Lepidoptera Survey is registered as a non-profit Limited Liability Company (LLC) in the state of Virginia, U.S.A. The Taxonomic Report (TTR), ISSN 2643-4776 (print) / ISSN 2643-4806 (online) is published for the purpose of providing a public and permanent scientific record. Articles are peer-reviewed but not necessarily through the anonymous editor-mediated review process. Typically, the authors are encouraged to solicit reviews of their manuscripts from knowledgeable lepidopterists before submission. TTR appears in digital, open-access form, is disseminated as a hardcopy to select institutional repositories, and is available as printed copy upon request at the discretion of authors and/or the editor. Printing and postage charges may apply. An initial run of 25 copies is printed on paper to meet ICZN Code recommendation 8B. All published TTR articles are freely available at the archival TTR website (<http://lepsurvey.carolinanature.com/report.html>) and via the following digital repositories:

Internet Archive (<https://archive.org/>)
Biodiversity Heritage Library (<https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org>)
Zobodat (<https://www.zobodat.at/>)
Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org>)
Digital Commons (<https://digitalcommons.unl.edu>)

TILS Purpose

TILS is devoted to the worldwide collection of Lepidoptera for the purpose of scientific discovery, determination, and documentation, without which there can be no preservation.

TILS Motto

“As a world community, we cannot protect that which we do not know”

Articles for publication are sought

Manuscripts may deal with any area of research on Lepidoptera, including faunal surveys, conservation topics, life histories and foodplant records, matters of nomenclature, descriptions of new taxa, methods, etc. Taxonomic papers are particularly welcome. There are no publication charges for authors. Before submitting a manuscript, email **TTR editor, Harry Pavulaan, 606 Hunton Place NE, Leesburg, VA, 20176, USA** at intlepsurvey@gmail.com (cc: to harrypav@hotmail.com if you do not receive a reply within one week) to initiate discussion on how to best handle your material for publication, and to discuss peer review options.

Visit *The International Lepidoptera Survey* on the World Wide Web at:

<http://lepsurvey.carolinanature.com>

&

Join the discussion at our list serve on Groups.io at:

<https://groups.io/g/TILS>

You can subscribe by sending an email to: TILS+subscribe@groups.io

&

Join The International Lepidoptera Survey on Facebook at:

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/1072292259768446>